

Russia-affiliated scholars publishing about internationalisation of higher education

A quantitative investigation based on OpenAlex

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This note is best viewed on-line at the following link:

<https://giorgiocomai.eu/post/2025-05-openalex-internationalisation-higher-education-russia/>

A preliminary note

This research note relies on OpenAlex to address the same question previously explored based on Scopus.

See the previous note in a web-version or as a pdf stored on Zenodo with a stable DOI (10.5281/zenodo.14791245).

Objective of this research note

Outline trends in the publication record of Russia-affiliated scholars writing about internationalisation of higher education.

Relying on OpenAlex's categorisation

OpenAlex automatically associates each publication to one or more concepts. Luckily, among the 65 073 concepts included in OpenAlex as of this writing, there is one which perfectly aligns with the objectives of this research note:

- concept c2778011250: Internationalization of Higher Education

	type	n
	article	2913
	book	53
	book-chapter	453
	dissertation	34
	editorial	3
	letter	1
	other	7
	paratext	3
	preprint	24
	reference-entry	2
	report	3
	retraction	1
	review	27
total	—	3524

Concepts are attributed to articles based on title, abstract, as well as the publication venue. For more details, see the official documentation.

OpenAlex includes a total of 3 524 works about “Internationalization of Higher Education”:

For consistency with the previous, Scopus-based analysis, we will focus exclusively on **journal articles** published **between 2011 and 2024**. This reduces the number of publications object of analysis to 2 205.

In brief, OpenAlex identifies 2 205 journal articles, including:

- 75 articles with at least an author with a Russian affiliation
- 1 505 articles with no author with a Russian affiliation
- 625 articles where the affiliation is not available (or, in a small number of cases, the country of the affiliation is not available)

It is possible to explore this subset of publications through OpenAlex’s interactive dashboard following this link: it shows only journal articles, published between 2011 and 2024, tagged with the concept “Internationalization of Higher Education”.

	Year	No Ru affiliation	Ru affiliation	Affiliation NA	Total	Ru share
	2011	81	1	25	107	0.06%
	2012	104	2	24	130	0.13%
	2013	123	0	45	168	0.00%
	2014	85	1	48	134	0.06%
	2015	87	5	58	150	0.32%
	2016	75	1	42	118	0.06%
	2017	104	2	59	165	0.13%
	2018	95	7	50	152	0.44%
	2019	113	9	50	172	0.57%
	2020	143	11	75	229	0.70%
	2021	177	17	40	234	1.08%
	2022	138	7	46	191	0.44%
	2023	125	10	31	166	0.63%
	2024	55	2	32	89	0.13%
Total	—	1505	75	625	2205	—

Number of publications about internationalisation of higher education

Counting relevant journal publications identified by OpenAlex

* 'Russian affiliation' attributed if at least one author is affiliated with a Russia-based institution
Not included when affiliation is not available or could not be attributed to any country.

Focus on publications by scholars with a Russian affiliation

By author

Authors of scholarly articles associated with 'internationalisation of higher education' published with a Russian affiliation. Ordered by number of publications; click on the cited by

column to order by number of times cited.

Table 1: Authors of scholarly articles associated with ‘internationalisation of higher education’ published with a Russian affiliation. Including only institutions with at least 3 publications or cited 10 times or more.

author	affiliation	publications	cited by
Elena Belyaeva	St Petersburg University	3	17
Anne Crowley Vigneau	Moscow State Institute of International Relations; University of Reading; School of International Relations	3	9
Andrey Baykov	Moscow State Institute of International Relations; University of Reading; School of International Relations	3	9
Yelena Kalyuzhnova	University of Reading; Moscow State Institute of International Relations; School of International Relations	3	9
Sergey M. Yun	National Research Tomsk State University	3	6
Elena V. Grigoryeva	Kazan Federal University	3	5
Abu Arif	University of Toronto; Memorial; Memorial University of Newfoundland	3	1
Д. М. Ковба	Ural Branch of the Russian Academy of Sciences	1	16
E. G. Gribovod	Ural Branch of the Russian Academy of Sciences	1	16
Julia Ziyatdinova	Kazan State Technological University	1	13
Vasily Ivanov	Kazan State Technological University	1	13
Lyudmila Kuznetsova	St Petersburg University	1	13

By institution

Russian institutions where scholars who published about ‘internationalisation of higher education’ were affiliated with. Ordered by number of publications.

Table 2: Authors affiliated with these Russia-based institutions have published about ‘internationalisation of higher education’. Including only institutions with at least 3 publications or cited 10 times or more.

affiliation	publications	cited by
St Petersburg University	5	27
Ural Branch of the Russian Academy of Sciences	2	19
Kazan State Technological University	1	13
Ural Federal University	5	11
National Research Tomsk State University	4	10
Moscow State Institute of International Relations	4	9
Yaroslav-the-Wise Novgorod State University	3	9
Kazan Federal University	5	8
The Russian Presidential Academy of National Economy and Public Administration	3	7

By article

Full list of articles on OpenAlex about “internationalisation of higher education” by at least one author with a Russian affiliation.

N.B. some items, although categorised by OpenAlex as articles, do not have information about the journal where they have been published; following their DOIs, these seems to be published in conference proceedings or similar. This issue involves 6 articles in total.

Table 3: List of articles with a Russian affiliation cited 5 times or more.

title	year	journal	cited by
International academic mobility through the prism of soft power theory	2020	The Education and science journal	16
Going Globally as a Russian Engineering University	2015	NA	13
IMPLEMENTING EMI AT A RUSSIAN UNIVERSITY: A STUDY OF CONTENT LECTURERS' PERSPECTIVES	2019	Journal of Teaching English for Specific and Academic Purposes	13
Fear of Brain Drain: Russian Academic Community on Internationalization of Education	2021	Journal of Studies in International Education	9
Internationalization of schools in Russia	2019	Policy Futures in Education	8
CROSS-CULTURAL COMMUNICATION COURSE AS A FORM OF INTERNATIONALISATION AT HOME WITHIN RUSSIAN HIGHER EDUCATION INSTITUTIONS	2018	SOCIETY INTEGRATION EDUCATION Proceedings of the International Scientific Conference	7
Internationalization of Higher Education: International Vector of the University Development Strategy	2018	Vysshee Obrazovanie v Rossii = Higher Education in Russia	7
Student Mobility as a Form of Education Internationalization: A Systems Approach to Management	2021	Vysshee Obrazovanie v Rossii = Higher Education in Russia	7
World-class Universities in Russia: A Contested Norm and its Implementation	2022	Journal of Studies in International Education	7
Internationalization of Higher Education in Russia: in Search for Development	2023	Vysshee Obrazovanie v Rossii = Higher Education in Russia	7
NEW FORMS OF UNIVERSITY COOPERATION: INTERNATIONAL NETWORKS OF UNIVERSITIES	2017	RUDN Journal of Economics	6
Prospects of Development of Export Potential of Higher Education of the Russian Federation	2018	Administrative Consulting	5
Students' International Academic Mobility in the Context of Internationalization of Higher Education (RUDN University Case)	2019	Vestnik RUDN International Relations	5
Adjustment or Inclusion?	2021	Journal of International Students	5

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